

Deployment of a cloud segmentation neural network on embedded hardware targets and benchmark of the different deployment toolchains.

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Abstract—Recently, the two Ops-Sat and Phi-Sat missions have demonstrated the feasibility of real-time cloud segmentation using neural networks onboard satellites. This process allows the data to be filtered so that only useful information is transmitted to the ground stations, reducing the need for data transmission. However, the experiments conducted on these missions are based on different neural network topologies and different hardware execution targets. On the Ops-Sat satellite, a LeNet-5 network was executed using a Cyclone V FPGA SoC, while a CloudScout network was executed on the Intel Movidius Myriad 2 ASIC of the Phi-Sat 1 mission. In this paper, we present how we trained and deployed a single tiny neural network (ANN) on various hardware targets: the FPGA SoC Critical Link MitySOM-5CSx (used on Ops-Sat) and two ASIC chips, the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (including a chip of the Myriad VPU family used on Phi-Sat) and the Google Coral. We then benchmark the deployment chains associated with the hardware targets. These deployment chains aim to compress the neural network model to make them compatible with the execution target. The performance evaluation is performed based on two criteria, the algorithmic performances and the hardware execution performances of the deployed models. Deployed models’ algorithmic performances were compared to those of the uncompressed trained model, using the accuracy, precision, recall and F-Score metrics. The results show that the F-score of the model deployed on the ASICs is more than 5 points higher than the one obtained on the FPGA. The hardware performances of the edge targets were compared based on latency, throughput, power and energy consumption. It was shown that with the hardware architecture developed, the FPGA is more than 11 times more efficient in terms of energy consumed per inference while having a latency more than 10 times lower than the one of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) ASICs.

Index Terms—Satellite Imagery, Hardware Architecture, FPGA, ASIC, Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Nano-Satellite, Cloud Segmentation, Embedded Systems

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I. INTRODUCTION

Clouds are estimated to cover more than 54% of the Earth’s land areas and 68% of the oceans [1]. To deal with the constant increasing amount of image data provided by Earth observation systems, numerous techniques have been developed to automate the cloud detection task in satellite image processing ground segments [2]–[5]. In the recent years, convolutional neural networks like U-Net [6], Fully Convolutional Networks (FCN) [7], SegNet [8] or DeepLabV3 [9] have raised the performance of semantic segmentation techniques far beyond the previous ones. For cloud detection in satellite images, UNET-like architectures such as CS-CNN [10] or CloudNet [11] have shown very good performances.

However, in an aerospace context, neural network deployment has to consider the available power [12] which restricts the possible choices of hardware accelerators that can be used. This is even more true when it comes to nano-satellite which have a limited solar panel area.

Two satellite missions have demonstrated the feasibility of on-board cloud segmentation using neural networks. In [13], authors used the FPGA of the OPS-SAT satellite launched on December 18th 2019. In [14] authors used the Myriad 2 VPU of the Phi-Sat satellite launched on September 3rd 2020. In this paper, we confront the deployment of the same neural network architecture on various hardware targets: an FPGA SoC (Critical Link MitySOM-5CSx) and two ASIC chips (the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 and the Google Coral).

II. RELATED WORK

ANNs for embedded Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications can be deployed on a wide variety of hardware targets. One of these, the standard Central Processing Unit (CPU), has small computational infrastructure and extended running times, that can prove inappropriate for time-restricted embedded applications. Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) are the most popular option for speeding up processing and reducing execution time. However, from an energy consumption point of view, Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) or Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) are more performant [15].

Today, there is a plethora of choices for Machine Learning (ML) hardware accelerators, such as NVIDIA's Jetson Nano [16]. In [17] authors made an end-to-end tool to benchmark different edge deep learning platforms. In the paper, the Google Edge TPU [18], the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2) [19] and the NVIDIA Jetson Xavier series [20] are benchmarked on three classification networks (Inception V3, MobileNet V2 and MnasNet B1) and one detection network (SSD-MobileNet V2). The Google Edge TPU is more efficient (images/s/W) against the Intel NCS2 for the MobileNet V2 and the MnasNet B1, and the Jetson Xavier outperforms both whatever the arithmetic used. But this paper do not benchmark tiny network such as Lenet like network.

A important aspect of our work is the semantic segmentation. Over the last few decades, semantic segmentation has continued to improve, and the state of the art is moving towards complex architectures of dozens of millions parameters [21]. These architectures require high computational resources that are not adapted with the goal to perform low latency inferences.

More recently, academics and industry are trying to build compact and edge-friendly networks embedded on edge devices. Authors in [22] made several cloud segmentation networks architecture losing around 5% accuracy but reducing complexity 100000 times against state-of-the-art architectures. An other approach in [23] [24] relies on a hardware-friendly neuromorphic network to perform cloud segmentation on FPGA.

In this paper, our contributions are:

- Compare the hardware of three edge devices MitySOM-5CSx (OPS-SAT), Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 (Phi-Sat-1 family) and Google Coral and their associated deployment workflows.
- Present our new Earth images dataset acquired by OPS-SAT and annotated by the CIAR project.
- Present the architecture and performances of our LeNet-5 like ANN trained on this new dataset.
- Compare post-deployment segmentation metrics for each devices in terms of Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F-score.
- Compare hardware performances for each devices in terms of Latency, Throughput, Power and Energy consumption.
- Discuss around software and hardware related metrics, and eventually confront them.

This article is structured as follows. Section II introduces recent works about edge devices benchmark and cloud segmentation at the edge. In Section III, we present each hardware targets used for the benchmark. Then in Section IV, we explain how we have deploy the ANN on each devices. In Section V we describe the CNN in detail. Results of the experiment are reported in Section VI and then findings are discussed in Section VII. Finally, in Section VIII we emphasize on our future works.

III. EVALUATION DEVICES

Our study is based on three hardware execution targets from different families. These targets have all been selected for their ability to accelerate neural networks inference. One of them belongs to the FPGA family, while the other targets are from the ASICs family. A Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is an integrated circuit designed to be configured after manufacturing. The FPGA configuration is specified using a "bitstream" file containing the configuration of the logic blocks and their interconnections. The FPGA reconfigurability allows the use of an accelerator architecture that is best suited to the operations to be accelerated.

In contrast, Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) are not hardware reconfigurable as the chip has been melted down for a given hardware architecture. When a chip is mass-produced, the use of ASIC technology can reduce costs compared to FPGAs.

It is interesting to compare the FPGA to the ASIC. The FPGA, thanks to its reconfigurability, allows the description of an accelerator specifically adapted to the neural network to be deployed. Whereas the two Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) ASICs use accelerators based on a generic architecture to allow the execution of different neural network topologies using software programming.

A. Critical Link MitySOM-5CSx

The MitySOM-5CSx is a highly configurable, small form-factor System-on-Module (SOM) embedded on the OPS-SAT nano-satellite launched on December 18th 2019. It combines the Altera Cyclone V System-on-Chip (SoC), memory subsystems, and an onboard power supplies. The Cyclone V 5CSXC6 SoC FPGA comprises a dual hard-core Cortex-A9 application processor, as well as 110K Logic Elements (LE) and 112 Digital Signal Processing (DSP) blocks. FPGAs are not exclusively dedicated to neural network inference. It is therefore necessary to develop an appropriate architecture for the studied case. This work is developed in subsection IV-A.

B. Intel Neural Compute Stick 2

The Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 is literally a stick with a USB port on it. It integrates the Intel Movidius Myriad X VPU (Vision Processing Unit) from the same family as the Myriad 2 VPU embedded on the Phi-Sat nano-satellite launched September 3rd 2020. More precisely, the Myriad X integrates 16 powerful processing cores (called SHAVE cores) at 700Mhz, a dedicated deep neural network hardware accelerator for high-performance vision and AI inference applications, 4Go RAM, and a USB 3.0 Type-A connection. Intel provides an open source OpenVINO toolkit with Python and C++ APIs, and an official OpenVINO™ graphical interface called OpenVINO Deep Learning (DL) Workbench to exploit Intel devices (CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs and VPUs, including this NCS2 stick).

C. Google Coral Development Board

Google Coral Development Board is an edge device allowing to build and test AI application. This evaluation board uses the edge version of the Google's TPU (Tensor Processing Unit). The Edge TPU is a purpose-built ASIC (Application Specific Integrated Circuit) providing high performance Machine Learning (ML) inferencing for TensorFlow Lite models.

This edge device, with its thousands of ALUs (Arithmetic Logic Units) and high TPU-to-memory data transfer rate, is made for matrix operation frequently used for neural network inference. In contrast to the two other hardware targets, the Coral has not been embedded in a nano-satellite, but it is relevant to test this target as the associated deployment chain (TFlite) is widely used in the field of embedded AI.

IV. ANN HARDWARE DEPLOYMENT WORKFLOWS

Hardware developers involved in this project share the same development and testing machines using a remote Secure Shell (SSH) access. In order to preserve the system libraries and to ease the try-and-remove software process where many engineers are involved in, we privilege Python virtual environment and/or Docker whenever it is possible, offering software portability and isolation. Each hardware execution targets presented has an associated hardware deployment toolchain. On the one hand, the deployment methodology associated with the MitySoM SoC FPGA rely on a custom hardware environment and on custom model optimisation scripts. On the other hand, ASIC manufacturers provide deployment tool-chains for their devices. These tools are generally sufficiently mature to make them easier to use than open source or custom tools.

A. Deployment on Critical Link MitySOM-5CSx

The CNN is trained using Tensorflow/Keras libraries to generate a ".h5" model file. To save logic cells occupation, float32 network's parameters are then converted to fixed-point numbers. This fixed-point arithmetic is defined according to the total memory allocation of the FPGA as described in [13]. The two components of fixed-point arithmetic are the integer part, which needs to have enough bits to prevent overflow in the different layers, and the fractional part, which needs to have as many bits as possible to have a precision as similar as possible to the one of the training model. Therefore, a balance between having enough precision and preventing overflow must be found. Several fixed-points FxPX.Y configurations have been tested, where X and Y bits are used respectively before and after the radix point. Our studies reveal that FxP8.9, which outperforms FxP8.8 by a significant margin, is the optimal compromise for this CNN model. The FxP7.10 arithmetic, on the other hand, results in overflows, which significantly lowers classification performance.

In the last step, the CNN HDL description is integrated in a complete Register Transfer Level (RTL) design defined using the Qsys tool. The used Qsys interfacing platform is detailed in [25]. Next, using the Quartus tool, the hardware architecture is synthesized and the bitstream is generated. The bitstream

is then loaded into a Cyclone's V FPGA which is similar to the one embedded in the orbital OPS-SAT satellite to perform on-ground cloud classification. Finally, the inference results are analyzed in the perspective of an in-orbit deployment.

The deployment of the CNN on FPGA required a much longer development time than the one used to embed the CNNs on the two COTS ASICs. Indeed, it was necessary to develop code to convert the 32-bit floating-point arithmetic of the h5 model to fixed-point, to develop VHDL code for the FPGA fabric configuration and to develop an embedded Java code that manages the data pre and post processing on the Cortex-A9 CPU. The added value of this solution is the ability to scale the deployment chain if the user's needs change. This also offers the possibility to better optimise the hardware platform compared to ASICs that have a frozen hardware accelerator architecture.

B. Deployment on Movidius chip

OpenVINO, an open source Software Development Kit (SDK) allowing AI inference optimization, tuning, running, on Intel devices, offers multiple Docker images. In our case, we rely on the model optimizer Python app embedded in the *ubuntu18_dev:2021.4* Docker image. To automatize as much as possible our processes, from the model conversion to the results analysis, we use ProActive (from Activeeon) [26], a job scheduling and workload automation that orchestrates our scripts through dedicated workflows. A workflow is an oriented graph of tasks, each task supporting multiple languages (Bash, Groovy, Python, R...), into which the user can copy paste his code (pre-processing, training, inference...). User can set a Docker environment execution for each task and, once submitted, each task executes on a ProActive node that can be deployed on any infrastructure (local machine, virtual machine in public cloud, FPGA, NCS2...). Our workflow consists in generating an Intermediate Representation model (as explained in [27]) from an ONNX model (OpenVINO/Docker/Bash). Then we can run the IR model to classify each patches (OpenVINO/Docker/Bash) with the stick plugged in our server. The output of this process is a well formatted classification .csv file (Groovy) that is converted in inference masks with a Python script. Finally a performance report is automatically generated (Bash/Matlab).

Using Docker for the OpenVINO tools caused some problems with NCS2 detection, requiring adjustments to the container launch command. Fortunately, the Intel OpenVINO community is very active.

C. Deployment on Google Coral Edge TPU

The Google Coral Edge TPU deployment when the network is already trained and with Google Coral's native setup required only few steps to perform inferences. First, the ".h5" network file is imported and converted into a base TensorFlow Lite Model. Then, using TensorFlow Lite Python API, the model is quantized into "fully integer" (weights in INT8 and biases in INT32) network via a Post-training Quantization and finally re-saved as a ".tflite" file. We have to remind

that the arithmetic choice of INT8 is imposed by the Google Coral. After that, with around 10 lines to code based on the TensorFlow Lite Python API, we can run the Python inference script on the Google Coral. This workflow is the most mature we have used, at least for our classification use case. Indeed, its compatibility with Tensorflow/Keras was a real advantage because we had a neural network stored in Keras format. Furthermore, the Tensorflow/Keras community and by extension Tensorflow Lite offers a flexible and comprehensive ecosystem. But, we can underline the fact that there is only one arithmetic available for inferences (weights in INT8 and biases in INT32). Besides that, two quantization methods are available : PTQ (Post-Training Quantization) [28] and QAT (Quantization-Aware Training).

V. CNN TRAINING AND PERFORMANCES

Figure 1: Earth image acquired by OPS-SAT’s camera (left) and on-board results of cloud detection (right) by an embedded ANN (Image credit: ESA)

A. OPS-SAT dataset

The CIAR project used a semi-manual pixel-level labeling technique to annotate the images that constitute the OPS-SAT cloud segmentation dataset. This dataset comes from the OPS-SAT satellite, which is located in a twilight sun-synchronous orbit. Refer to [13] for more information. As a result, the produced images show a significant solar illumination variability that influences the ANN performance. We use the method outlined in [13] to segment this dataset using classification ANNs. It entails dividing the OPS-SAT data images into smaller patches and assigning a label to each patch. Since the ANN model used is LeNet-5, the images are split into $28 \times 28 \times 3$ non-overlapping patches. Those are divided into two classes based on the amount of cloud coverage. According to their cloud coverage, which ranges from 0% (cloud-free patch) to 100% (all-cloud patch), a cloud or no-cloud label is assigned. The dataset has recently grown from 19 images to 37 images of $2048 \times 1944 \times 3$ pixels, gathering 186369 $28 \times 28 \times 3$ classification patches. Additionally, we decided to use a largest train set for solar illumination. As a result, 29 images (146073 patches) are used for the learning phase.

B. CNN model topology and training method

In [13], four ANN architectures are presented. The Convolutional Neural Network, as described in Table I, is selected as

Figure 2: OPS-SAT dataset examples. Top: dataset full image with cloud and snow. Bottom: dataset full image showing saturated and dark clouds. Left: RGB images. Right: images overlaid by a cloud ground-truth (yellow=cloud, magenta=no-cloud)

reference model for this paper. This is a LeNet-like topology having a $28 \times 28 \times 3$ input and two output neurons representing the binary cloud/no-cloud classes gathering 1440 learning parameters. This model implements convolutional and fully connected layers whose impacts is interesting to evaluate on selected execution targets. Using the Tensorflow/Keras library, we have built and trained the CNN model on the training set. Note that the output of classification CNN (1×1) are up-scaled to $28 \times 28 \times 1$ size output segmentation maps. Thus, processing all the patches of the original $2048 \times 1944 \times 3$ size image results in an output segmentation map with the same size. Once a patch is classified by the CNN, the AI performance is assessed versus the ground truth at pixel level, as shown in Figure 2, impacting negatively the AI metrics. However, the same approach is applied to each target and does not affect the final confrontation. Metrics are reported in Table II.

Table I: CNN topology

Layer	Units	Filters	Kernel	Stride	Bias	Activation
Conv2D	-	3	5x5	1x1	true	ReLU
Pool2D	-	-	2x2	2x2	-	-
Conv2D	-	5	5x5	1x1	true	ReLU
Pool2D	-	-	2x2	2x2	-	-
Dense	10	-	-	-	true	ReLU
Dense	2	-	-	-	true	SoftMax

C. Baseline CNN model performances

In this section we will briefly comment Table II showing performance results of the CNN when performing cloud segmentation based on patches classification. An example of a segmentation map result of an original real scale image is shown in Figure 1. The Table II refers to a previous model trained on the old dataset (19 images), and our model trained with the last dataset (37 images). An other difference between these two models is the framework and the hyper-parameters

used. The CNN (“In [13]”) was trained with MATLAB and the new one (“Our work”) was trained with Tensorflow/Keras, applying these hyper-parameters :

- . 150 Epochs
- . Batch Size of 8 patches
- . Early Stopping on best Validation Accuracy with a patience of 5 epochs
- . Binary Crossentropy loss function
- . Adam optimizer with learning rate sets to 0.001

Unsurprisingly, the new model significantly outperforms the older one on most performance metrics, except for the Precision which is very close (< 1%).

Table II: Performances Table of the CNN on GPU (Float32)

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Fscore
In [13]	67.85	79.13	51.60	62.46
Our work	80.90	78.34	87.32	82.58
Our gain	13.05	-0.59	35.72	20.12

VI. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

A. Inference performances and analysis

In this section, we present the software-related results of the deployments of the CNN presented in Table I on the different hardware targets. We chose to use four evaluation metrics for the comparison, Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F-score, that are defined below :

- Accuracy, here Pixel Accuracy

$$accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

- Precision

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

- Recall

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

- F-score also know as F1-score

$$F_1 = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall}$$

with T = True, F = False, P = Positive, N = Negative

Table III: CNN’s inference performances on the different hardware targets

All results have been obtained on the test set of 8 images (40, 296 patches). MitySoM model is entirely in FxP8.9 (8 bits for integer part, and 9 bits for fractional part) and Movidius in Float16. Coral model is in “TFL” arithmetic, meaning weights are encoded in int8 and bias are in int32 [29].

Performance Metric	Hardware Target			
	Baseline (Float 32)	Cyclone V (FxP8.9)	Myriad X (Float 16)	Edge TPU (TFL)
Accuracy	80.90	77.89	81.28	80.84
F-score	82.58	77.25	82.92	82.41
Precision	78.34	82.80	78.68	78.62
Recall	87.32	72.40	87.63	86.59

Results of inferences on the test set over the different targets are summarized in Table III and synthesized in the Figure 3.

First, we have to mention that for the MitySoM, except for the Precision gaining +5.69%, every metrics decreased, from around -4% in Accuracy and F-score, to more than -17% in Recall, knowing that the bit-width used is the highest that can fit in the FPGA (FxP8.9) considering the resources available on the Cyclone V.

The overall performance degradation of the CNN on the MitySoM is explained by the use of a homogeneous fixed-point arithmetic between all layers of the network. This choice was made to facilitate the hardware description code used for the FPGA deployment. While, the quantification applied with the TensorFlow Lite deployment chain, renormalizes the intermediate results between the different layers of the neural network. This effectively manages the evolution of the dynamic of cross-layer results. Refer to VIII for more details about our future works and how we plan to improve algorithmic performance on FPGAs.

Furthermore, we can clearly notice that there is no notable differences from Movidius and Coral performances compared to the Float32 baselines, the biggest error of -0.84% coming from Coral’s Recall. The objective of this work is also to quantify the hardware deployment costs of the same neural model on several targets with different hardware architectures.

B. Hardware performances and analysis

This section aims at giving and analysing the hardware performance for each of the targets based on latency, throughput, power and energy consumption. The results obtained are summarised in the Table IV.

The perimeter of hardware performance measurements focuses on the image inference in the CNN. Pre- and post-processing, such as slicing the original satellite image into 5037 small 28x28 patches, is not included in this measure. Indeed, depending on the hardware targets architectures, these operations are not always executed on the edge. For instance, the Intel Neural Compute Stick 2 is connected to a host server that is responsible for executing the processing around the network. Doing this gives us comparable values between hardware accelerators.

A hardware metric of interest is the execution latency in order to meet the response time constraints of the embedded system. Latency is the duration between the moment the first pixel of an image is sent to the network for inference and the moment the prediction is generated.

For the Cyclone V and Edge TPU, we can see in Table IV that the latency to infer 5037 28 × 28 pixel patches is directly proportional to the latency of one patch. The reason is that these architectures involve inferring images in batches of 1, without any batch processing optimisation such as operation overlapping. In this situation, the throughput is the inverse of the latency. The OpenVino tool associated with the Intel Movidius Myriad X has the possibility of privileging throughput or latency. The first case of operation allows images to be executed synchronously: inference is

Figure 3: Performances (in %) of the CNN on different targets

Table IV: CNN latency and power consumption results for 28×28 pixel patches inference on the three hardware targets. $((i))$: means synchronous mode, $((j))$: means asynchronous mode, $((k))$: means maximum power consumption estimation

Performance Metrics		Hardware Target		
		Cyclone V	Myriad X	Edge TPU
Latency over number of patches (μ s)	1	24.8	2 097.0 (i)	254.6
	5037	125 104	2 241 465 (i)	1 282 370
(1/Throughput) over number of patches (μ s)	1	24.8	1 993.0 (j)	254.6
	5037	125 104	1 566 507 (j)	1 282 370
Mean power consumption (W)		1.7 ± 0.12	2 (k)	2 (k)
Energy consumption for one patch (μ J)		42.7	622.0	509.18

Figure 4: Latency, Throughput and Energy metrics of each targets (\uparrow means higher is better, \downarrow means lower is better)

performed without any batch processing optimisation such as operation overlapping, as for the Edge TPU and the Cyclone V. This solution is best suited to measure the latency. In Table IV, the latency is calculated with OpenVINO default settings (stream of size 2), in synchronous mode, to infer one patch and a batch of 5037 patches corresponding to the full image. Inferring 5037 patch batches rather than 1 unique patch reduces the latency by a factor of 4.7. Another solution called asynchronous execution allows performing batch-processing optimisation such as operation overlapping. It favour throughput at the expense of the latency. With synchronous setting the throughput is strictly the invert of the

latency. It is clearly not applicable in the asynchronous mode. Using large batch size, in asynchronous mode, improved by factor 6.4 the throughput by extrapolating the result to one patch.

When comparing the performances of the Edge TPU with the ones of the Myriad X, the latency of the Edge TPU is 42% lower than that of the Myriad X in the most optimized configuration of the Myriad X. Edge TPU throughput is 18% higher than Myriad X throughput in the most Myriad X friendly configuration. Both for throughput and latency, Edge TPU performs better than Myriad X. Despite of the best temporal performances of the Edge TPU, it should be noted that the order of magnitude of performance is similar between these 2 targets. On the other hand, the FPGA's temporal performance is more than 10 times higher than the one of the COTS ASICs, as shown in Figure 4. This can be explained by the fact that the hardware architecture is specifically dedicated to the inference of the CNN architecture. Whereas the ASICs' architectures are generic.

To achieve these performances, the design uses 82.79% of ALMs as described in the Table V that shows the post-routing results of the CNN accelerator. As detailed in the subsection IV-A, the FxP8.9 arithmetic used for CNN inference was chosen to take advantage of the available area in the FPGA.

The average power consumed by the CNN accelerator

Table V: Resource usage of the Cyclone V

FPGA Resource	ALMs (%)	82.79
	Registers (%)	68.32
	BRAM (%)	24.41
	DSPs (%)	0.00

was measured on the Cyclone V directly on the OPS-SAT demonstrator. The results are detailed in the Table V. The mean power consumption of the FPGA’s Programmable Logic part is $1.72W$ during the execution.

For the Edge TPU and the Movidius Myriad X we have based ourselves on the estimated consumptions provided by the manufacturers. Intel announces $0.5W$ to $2W$ power consumption of its Myriad X [30]. Unfortunately the OpenVINO API we used doesn’t allow measuring memory and power consumption on the Myriad X as explained in [31]. For the Google TPU, the estimated power consumption is announced to $2W$ as shown in [32].

However, it is interesting to study energy consumption for one patch inference. The energy consumed during image inference is the product of the average power consumed and the processing time. The power consumption being of the same order of magnitude for the different targets, the execution time has an impact on the energy consumed per inference. We can see in the Table IV that the execution on Cyclone V consumes almost 12 times less energy than on the Edge TPU and from 3.7 to 14.6 times less energy than the Myriad X.

VII. DISCUSSIONS

According to the software and hardware metrics we collected, the following section intends to help in decision-making on the best suited hardware device given a use case.

To perform the selection, we need to make a compromise between the metrics we mentioned in VI. Considering use cases highly sensitive to segmentation performances, the AI metrics must be a primary criteria of a device selection, and the Myriad X would be selected. However the Myriad X latency is $445\mu s$, so system requiring a very low response time should select the Cyclone V with a latency of $24.8\mu s$. In the aerospace context, where a large amount of data must be processed in a given time, throughput is a major hardware target selection factor. Ideally an image should be processed before the next one is captured. On this metric too, the MitySoM is the most beneficial target. Based on the ASIC’s manufacturers inputs, the Cyclone V seems to be the best choice for a very limited power/energy system or with limited charging possibilities. Note that regarding the power consumption, all accelerators could be used on a demonstrator like OPS-SAT because their power is approximately $2W$.

It is also important to highlight the ease of use of the deployment workflows. As expected the COTS ASICs are much easier to use than the FPGA, but the study showed that the TFLite tool associated with the Google Coral is the most mature of the tools used here.

In order to perform a qualitative selection, the different metrics are displayed on the same Figure 5.

Figure 5: Metrics confrontation for each hardware accelerator

VIII. FURTHER IMPROVEMENTS

In this benchmark, we considered that the power consumption values provided by the manufacturer VI-B are sufficiently precise. But in the future we want to try measuring the full power consumption of several devices. To do this we could keep the Google Coral Dev Board and the MitySOM-5CSx, but we will need at least an evaluation board with the Myriad X integrated because using the NCS2 USB-plugged on a SBC (Single-Board Computer) or a micro-controller like the Raspberry Pi will involve too much exchanges between the stick and the SBC. For a fair comparison it is necessary to compare equivalent boards with similar memories and interfaces.

In a further work, we plan to update the workflow of the MitySoM to reduce performance losses during deployment. The solution will rely on a homemade generic library over which we have a total control. We plan to add a normalisation or "re-quantization" block between each layer to prevent overflow. This block will act as an activation which will re-clamp (restrict values between two other numbers) layer’s outputs in the range allowed by the arithmetic (e.g. [-128;127] for INT8). Moreover, we are thinking of ways to be able to perform layer-wise quantization [33], meaning we could use a different arithmetic for each layer. In this paper we compared the Cyclone V to the Myriad X which is a VPU of the same family as the Myriad 2 embedded on Phi-Sat 1. In the future, we really want to be able to compare our OPS-SAT deployment based on the Cyclone V SoC FPGA with the Phi-Sat-1 solution based on the Myriad 2 VPU. Work is underway to complete this deployment. Furthermore we are open to set up a collaboration with Philab for example by exchanging data to effectively compare our results, workflows and eventually our feedbacks.

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